

Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria?

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 12 October 2022

Revised 29 Nov. 2022

Accepted 18 December 2022

Published 13 January 2023

Keywords:

Leverage, CEO's Overconfidence,
Gender Diversity, Nigerian
Exchange Group

JEL Classification:

F20, G21, G32,
G41

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the influence of chief executive officers on leverage decisions of listed firms in Nigeria for a period of 10 years (2012-2021). In this paper, chief executive officer is proxied by three characteristics (overconfidence, age, and gender) while leverage is proxied by leverage ratio. We use panel data for 116 companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The results of our study reveal that chief executive officer's overconfidence and gender are positively and significantly related to leverage. However, chief executive officer's age is negatively and significantly associated with leverage. These findings are of interest to researchers, policymakers, regulators and scholars. Furthermore, these findings are useful to investors and corporate boards. Our study contributes to research into leverage by examining a different dimension, that is, the influence of chief executive officer on financial leverage. However, like other empirical works, this paper's findings are limited to firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Also, in view of the listing requirements which make way for transparency and accountability, we sampled only listed companies. In addition, we were unable to consider all related factors affecting financial leverage.

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Introduction

Organizations making debt decisions are one of the most studied areas in corporate finance (Harris & Raviv, 1991; Zeitun & Tian, 2007). Since the classic thesis of Myers and Majluf (1984) on the irrelevance of leverage in investment decisions, a rich theoretical literature has appeared on this type of power from leverage options to different frames. Many theories like business theory are based on traditional factors such as tax benefits and debt that can be paid if it pays, while others use asymmetric information or game systems. -theoretic in which debt or equity is used as a benchmark. strategy or planning tool (Desai et al., 2005; Myers & Majluf, 1984; Ross, 1977). Many of these theories have been empirically tested, but there is little consensus on how firms make debt decisions (Lemmon et al., 2014). This article examines the role of CEOs in choosing leverage. A growing body of research in experimental psychology reports that people often deviate from this traditional approach. Managers tend to be overly optimistic and overconfident. That is, they predict that what will happen in the future is better than it is, they believe that they have better knowledge about what will happen in the future than they actually have (Libby & Rennekamp, 2012; Skala, 2008). It is likely that business leaders have certain characteristics that are often said to have a certain influence on corporate decisions. Therefore, it is important to understand how these management characteristics affect the results of the company and therefore the interests of the shareholders. Most studies on the relationship between leverage and CEOs focus on developed countries (Cronqvist et al., 2012; Malmendier et al., 2011), although the world economic system varies in context. located in developing countries is greatly affecting the global economic recovery. Business in Nigeria, as an emerging market, is attracting more attention. Given this perspective, we examine the relationship between leverage and CEOs in the Nigerian context, and particularly among companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

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This article examines the influence of the CEO on decision leverage; this is different from previous studies that tried to explain the relationship between debt and different factors such as firm performance (Ahmad et al., 2012) or return of shareholders (Salawu & Agboola, 2008a). A review of previous studies has not been clear about how senior executives affect leverage. These limitations motivate the current study to fill this gap in the literature. Therefore, the objective of this study is to extend the existing literature by examining the effect of CEO (confidence level, age and gender) on leverage options among Nigerian companies during the period 2012-2021, this and - often mentioned as important. CEO for corporate decision making (Frank & Goyal, 2007; Li et al., 2017). The results reveal that the degree of trust in gender is closely related to the degree of leverage as a proxy for leverage. However, age is negatively and significantly associated with leverage. Therefore, this study contributes to the literature on leverage by examining another aspect, namely the influence of the CEO, which has not been studied before in debt decisions, and provides new evidence in this field. In particular, our evidence is well supported by Morellec (2004), showing that management control is an important determinant of leverage policy. Furthermore, this study contributes to the literature by adding interesting evidence to the debate about the importance of the CEO in business results and, ultimately, overall business value.

Literature Review

In corporate finance, the leverage effect is a very important part of the choice of funds since it affects the return on equity and the risks associated with ownership and the market value of shares (Frank & Goyal, 2009). However, the wrong combination of funds can cause serious damage affecting the performance and survival of business enterprises (Thomas et al., 2014). As the highest and most powerful leader, the CEO can influence the company's decision making (Carpenter et al., 2004). In addition, the CEO's influence on investment and financial decisions, his characteristics and his preference for risk factors affect the company's debt policy (Chen et al., 2014). Risk-averse managers can use the tax advantage of interest on debt to direct higher income; while risk managers tend to hold more capital to avoid the financial stress of leverage, which damages reputation. In response, researchers began to examine individual characteristics, including that of the CEO (Faccio et al., 2016; Huang & Kisgen, 2013; Serfling, 2014). Faccio et al. (2016) and Li et al. (2017) show the importance of managers in leverage decisions. For example, Faccio et al. (2016) document that female directors are more likely to be associated with less risky companies that are less capital intensive, have less volatile income, and are more likely to survive. Similarly, Armstrong et al. (2010) suggested that CEO characteristics may play an important role in the choice of leverage, as executives are selected to meet shareholders' expectations to maximize firm profits. Similarly, Malmendier et al. (2011) showed that the characteristics of the CEO have a significant impact on the financial decision of the company. Although the CFO has the main responsibility for making financial decisions, it is the directors of the company who decide whether to make money externally or use money and debt without risk. Salawu and Agboola (2008b) document that corporate leverage is considered an important management decision because it affects the shareholders' return on equity, the shareholders' risk as well as the market value of shares.

In recent time, the literature in corporate finance has focused on the influence of the personality traits of business leaders on debt selection (Cronqvist et al., 2012; Faccio et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017; Malmendier et al., 2011). According to Hambrick (2007), senior managers influence judgments and decisions, and among these qualities is confidence. Overconfidence is the tendency of individuals to consider themselves above average (Alicke, 1985; Kruger, 1999; Svenson, 1981). Langer (1975) defined self-confidence as "assessing one's own abilities and outcomes in relation to one's personal situation". The CEO of the trust can influence the debt ratio/equity selection, he will choose to issue more debt than his peers (Alqatamin et al., 2017). This happens because the short-sighted CEO believes that the company is less likely to experience financial problems than it actually is (Hackbarth, 2008). Trustworthy CEOs tend to be more responsible and pay dividends because they believe it can provide more shareholder value (Graham et al., 2013). However, Malmendier et al. (2007) show that conservative managers use higher debt ratios than rational managers. As a result, he will underestimate the amount expected to be lost and take on more debt in order to benefit from his taxes. Weinstein (1980) and Alicke (1985) previously reported that trust is often found in managers (Cooper et al., 1988; Landier & Thesmar, 2009). The effect of CEO distrust on corporate decision making has received considerable attention in the academic literature. For example, Malmendier and Tate (2008) and Frank and Goyal (2009) document that it can have a significant impact on the change in debt between companies. Fairchild (2010) examines the impact of management confidence on investment decisions, using two models: the company's problem of leaving money and the company's problem with management contracts. However, in both cases, the feeling of overconfidence is confusing. Oliver (2009) examined the relationship between CEO trust and debt ratios among the 500 largest companies in the US. The results concluded that leaders are more likely to give compensation when they are rated as overly trusting. However, the research of Tomak (2013) on the relationship between trust and remuneration in 117 Turkish companies, from 2002 to 2011, showed that the relationship between the variables is complex, since and there is not enough evidence that reliable managers can use the standard is high debt.

Taylor (1975) noted that managerial decisions and performance vary with age and decision-making experience. Previous studies have provided conflicting predictions about how age affects risky behavior and investing. One part of the literature argues that young leaders use other factors to work and the other argues that the opposite is true. Serfling (2014) documents that CEO characteristics such as age are associated with pay behavior, with older CEOs investing less than younger CEOs in order to live comfortably. The results of the study support the argument that older CEOs may have less risk because they tend to think about the past, while younger CEOs think about the future (Chen et al., 2014). Bertrand and Schoar (2003) and Frank and Goyal (2007) also argue that older CEOs are associated with conservative behavior due to past experience, but younger CEOs are more prone to "because of their expectations for the future. Therefore, the first people avoid paying debt, although their study did not find significant evidence to support their argument.

The third demographic characteristic examined in the literature is the gender of the CEO (Richardson et al., 2016). For example, Singh and Zammit (2000) studied the effect of gender on international influence. It is argued that women leaders lose out more than their male counterparts in an underpaid economy. Men are often concerned about financial gain and successful careers, and often break rules and regulations to achieve competitive advantage, while women learn more about proper relationships and helping others, it is difficult ability to engage in negative situations (Mason & Mudrack, 1996). Huang and Kisgen (2013) found that companies led by men are more likely to incur debt than companies led by women. Graham et al. (2013) showed that companies led by men are more indebted than those led by women. Similarly, Faccio et al. (2016) analyzed 21 countries between 1999 and 2009 and found a significant relationship between female directors and leverage ratio. The idea of superiority assumes that men are too brave and risk-averse; while women, on the contrary, are more protective and risky (Huang & Kisgen, 2013). The same theory describes women leaders as conservative, preferring to invest equity rather than pay debt (Frank & Goyal, 2007). In

other words, female leaders are more conservative and risk-averse and therefore more likely to use less debt (Faccio et al., 2016; Huang & Kisgen, 2013). Thus, based on these results, we suggest that:

H₁: CEO overconfidence and leverage are related.

H₂: CEO age and leverage are correlated.

H₃: Leverage and the presence of male CEOs are associated.

Methodology

The study collated data from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), which listed 155 companies. All technically suspended companies (39) were excluded from the sample for purposes ranging from restructuring to regulatory compliance (NGX, 2021). Therefore, the final sample consisted of 116 companies covering the years 2012-2021, and 1,160 company-year observations, as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Sample

Description	Pooled
Sample:	1160
Financial services	41
Non-financial services	75
Sectors:	
Health Care	24
Technology and Communication	6
Media	12
Paper and Cardboard	18
Utilities and Energy	18
Printing and Packaging	6
Tobacco and Cigarettes	12
Glass and Ceramic Industries	6
Banks	13
Insurance	1

Table 2

Sample by industry

Description	Percentage
Educational services	12.93%
Hotels and tourism	18.90%
Transport	11.44%
Commercial services	20.39%
Pharmaceutical and medical industries	5.97%
Chemical industries	7.46%
Food and beverages	8.45%
Mining and extraction industries	6.96%
Engineering and construction	2.98%
Textiles, leather and clothing	4.47%
Total	100%

This data was collected from annual reports published in the years 2012-2021. Each data is hand-picked. The annual report is available on the NGX website. Most companies publish their annual reports in the first quarter of the following fiscal year. Annual reports are perceived to be easier among companies than other less effective communication channels such as press releases or direct contact surveys (Alqatamin et al., 2017; Chang & Most, 1985). Leverage is a variable based on our return model. We measure leverage as the book value of total long-term debt divided by the book value of total assets, using data obtained from each financial statement company (Wen et al., 2002; Zeitun et al., 2007; Olokoyo, 2013). Following previous studies (Andriosopoulos et al., 2013; Cornett et al., 2008; Cornett et al., 2009; Davidson III et al., 2007; Lin et al., 2014; Skalpe, 2007), the study age was measured as the difference between the date of birth and the age of birth. Gender of the CEO is a dummy variable with a value of 1 if the CEO is male and 0 if female (Skalpe, 2007; Yu et al., 2010; Andriosopoulos et al., 2013; Yim, 2013).

To measure overconfidence, we use the Net Buyer method, which focuses on the option to hold actions and buy products. Following Malmendier and Tate (2008) and Alqatamin et al. (2017). This measure depends on the desire of CEOs to buy more shares in their company despite exposing their own wealth to a high level of business risk. In fact, overconfident CEOs look at their own stock's potential returns, believing that the company's stock price will rise more under their leadership than it has. look forward to it. If the CEO has such a strong belief, he wants to buy shares of the company hoping to enjoy the expected income in the future. Therefore, we defined the CEO as overconfident based on the size of the net buyer if he was the buyer of his own company's stock during the first ten years of the sample. It should be understood that in finding courage in a leader, he is described as a courageous person for all ages. A dichotomous variable is created with 1 representing high confidence and 0 otherwise.

To control for corporate and governance characteristics that affect leverage, the study adds firm size, profit, division, sector, board size, duality, board independence, board meetings, family size, control size, and -hold restrictions on company boundaries. Previous studies suggest that these changes can affect leverage (Berger et al., 1997; Olokoyo, 2013; Wen et al., 2002). This model examines the relationship between leverage and CEO. Table 3 provides descriptions and measurements of all variables. Equation (1) is the model of the study.

$$LEV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEOA_{it} + \beta_2 CEOG_{it} + \beta_3 CEOO_{it} + \beta_4 FS_{it} + \beta_5 PROF_{it} + \beta_6 DIV_{it} + \beta_7 IND_{it} + \beta_8 BS_{it} + \beta_9 BOARD_{it} + \beta_{10} BOARDI_{it} + \beta_{11} BOARDM_{it} + \beta_{12} BOARDIN_{it} + \beta_{13} MANAOW_{it} + \beta_{14} FAMILow_{it} + \beta_{15} INSTITOW_{it} + \beta_{16} BLOCKOW_{it} + \text{Industry Controls}_{it} + \text{Year Controls}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Whereas:

β_0 = The regression intercept; $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{16}$ = The regression coefficients; ε = The error term.

Table 3
Variables, definitions, and measurements

Label	Variable	Description
FLEVER	Leverage Ratio	Used as a proxy for leverage measured by total long-term debt divided by total assets.
CAGE	CEO's Age	Measured by the difference between the CEO's date of birth and the years of the study period.
CGEND	CEO's Gender	A dummy variable taking value 1 if CEO male, and 0 if CEO female.
COVER	CEO's Overconfidence	Measured using: Net Buyer: dummy variable taking value 1 if the proportion of CEO share ownership, options and stock exercise increases, and 0 otherwise.
FSIZE	Firm Size	The natural log of a firm's total assets.
FPROF	Firm Profitability	Measured by ROA (net income before tax divided by total assets).
FDIVID	Dividends Ratio	Cash dividends divided by net income for the same period.
FINDUST	Industry Type	A dummy variable that takes the value of 1 in the company operates under manufacturing sector and 0 if operates under service sector.
BOARDSI	Board Size	Measured by the total numbers of the board.
BOARDDD	Board Duality	A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the CEO and chairman are the same person and zero otherwise.
BBOARDM	Board Meeting	The number of meetings per year held by the board of directors.
MANAOW	Managerial Ownership	Measured by the proportion of total shares held by executive directors divided by the total number of shares.
FAMILow	Family Ownership	Measured by the proportion of total shares owned by the family. Dummy variable takes 1 if a family or individual holds 10% or more of equity and 0 otherwise.
INSTITOW	Institutional Ownership	Measured by dummy variable would take one if any institutional-held shares and zero otherwise.
BLOCKOW	Block holder Ownership	A dummy variable that takes the value 1 if the firm has an external stockholder owning 5% or more of the outstanding shares, and 0 otherwise.

Results and Discussion

Table 4 shows that the average value of leverage is (0.295), compared to 29% reported by Frank and Goyal (2009). However, the minimum and maximum values of the leverage ratio are (0.002) and (0.978) respectively with a standard deviation (Std.) of (0.2320). The average age is 51.11 years with a range of 26 to 84 years and a median value of 51 years. This result compares to previous studies, such as Custódio and Metzger (2014) and (Serfling, 2014), which both find an average age of 52. The median age is used as a threshold to distinguish between older and younger presidents. Furthermore, descriptive results show that 95% of CEOs are male and 5% of CEOs are female. These percentages are lower than the comparative studies of Huang and Kisgen (2013) and (Faccio et al., 2016) which write 6.2% and 9.4% respectively. Table 4 shows that 43% of CEOs are overconfident about their company's performance using the procurement process.

Regarding the management variable, the value of the company size shows that the company is widely dispersed, ranging from 0.9303 to 3.2309. The results reveal that the value differs between the minimum value of -85.90% (loss) and 95% (maximum value), with a SD of 12.17%. The corporate model had an average value of 36.3% with SD (48.11). Also, Table 4 shows that the average value of the distribution ratio is 18.82%, the minimum and maximum values are 0 and 97.51% respectively, so the median value is zero (SD = 30.77%). Board size has an average value of 8.011, which is consistent with the reported number (Peasnell et al., 2005). However, the highest number is 19 members, indicating that in general, Nigerian companies do not comply with the number of Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance which supports the maximum 13 members (NGX, 2015). A dummy variable of board duality has a mean of 0.205, and the minimum and maximum values for the number of board meetings are 3 and 28, respectively. Freedom Board has a mean value of 2.020. Regarding the structure of ownership, management and family have average values of 0.352 and 0.19 respectively, while companies and blocks have values of 0.355 and 0.435 respectively.

Table 4
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
FLEVER	.0002	.9780	.295	.232
CAGE	26	84	51.41	11.26
CGEND	0	1	.9519	.214
COVER	0	1	.435	.491
FSIZE	.93	3.23	5.55	1.57
FPROFIT	-.859	.950	.001	.121
FSECTOR	0	1	.363	.481
FDIVID	0	.9751	.188	.307
BOARDSI	3	19	8.01	2.44
BOARDDD	0	1	.205	.404
BOARDM	3	28	7.57	2.13
BOARDI	0	8	2.02	1.23
MANAOW	0	.7185	.035	.085
FAMILLOW	0	.945	.190	27.20
INSTITOW	0	1	.355	.272
BLOCKOW	0	1	.435	.451

A correlation coefficients matrix was used to check for the incidence of multicollinearity between independent variables, as employed extensively in previous disclosure literature (Abdel-Fattah, 2008; Alqatamin et al., 2017). Table 5 shows that the highest correlation is between the board size and board independence, with a coefficient of 41.54 percent. Therefore, Table 5 confirms that the multicollinearity problem does not exist in the data set used in this study. To achieve investigate the relationship between CEOs' personal characteristics and leverage choices, a panel regression random-effect method was used; the results are presented in Table 6. The R² value is 71.6 percent, which means that the independent variable demonstrates 71.6 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. The P-value is highly significant at the level (P > .000), meaning that the model is highly significant and thus has a good explanatory power of disclosure. The analysis of results shows a significant and positive relationship between CEOs' overconfidence and leverage ratio as a proxy for leverage at the level (P < .001). This result supports H1, which suggested that there is a positive relationship between CEO overconfidence and debt level among non-financial Nigerian companies. Our results are consistent with the study of Fairchild's (2005) and Malmendier et al. (2011) who found a positive and significant relationship between CEOs' overconfidence and leverage ratio. This result indicates that the higher the level of leverage ratio, the higher will be the CEO's overconfidence, which suggests that specific personal characteristics of top management affect the decision-making process (Hambrick, 2007). A possible explanation for these findings is that overconfident managers are more likely to be more optimistic about future circumstances, overestimating their own abilities and issuing a high portion of debt. In respect to the CEO's age, we document a negative significant coefficient (P < .006), which implies a significant relationship between the leverage and the CEO's age. This result provides support for the prediction that younger CEOs are bolder and use riskier financing than older CEOs, which is consistent with the predictions of Serfling (2014), who reported that age is associated with debt financing behavior. The result also supports the prediction of Hambrick and Mason (1984) that older managers have less physical and mental stamina, and therefore value financial security and stability by reducing leverage. This finding is also consistent with several studies that reported a significant negative association between the CEO's age and other factors such as investment decision (Serfling, 2012; Yim, 2013). The results of our study indicate that older managers tend to avoid risks more than do younger managers; younger managers want to show their capability to stakeholders. Therefore, H2 is supported. The third hypothesis is related to gender, that male CEOs take more risks than female and as a result, employ higher levels of debt. Therefore, the third regression result is for CEOs' gender. It scored a positive and significant relationship to firm leverage ratio at level (P < .001). Thus, H3 is supported. The finding indicates that companies managed by male CEOs are associated with a higher leverage ratio than those managed by female CEOs. The result suggests that males more confident and may even be overconfident. As a result, they are more likely to undertake more debt in the same operational conditions. Their confident in their management ability makes them believe that more debt would bring higher return. This finding confirms that gender diversity is one of the attributes influencing leverage decisions.

Table 5. Correlation Matrix

variables	CGEND	CAGE	COVER	F SIZE	F PROF	F SECTO	F DIVID	B SIZE	B DUAL	B MEET	B INPEN	M OWNE	F OWNE	INSTIT	B LOCK
CGEND	1.000														
CAGE	0.073**	1.000													
COVER	-0.148**	-0.048	1.000												
F SIZE	0.020	0.025	0.017	1.000											
F PROF	0.016	-0.008	-0.007	0.043	1.000										
F SECTO	0.092**	-0.024	0.117**	0.068**	0.371**	1.000									
F DIVID	-0.152**	0.082**	0.206**	0.032	-0.156**	0.034	1.000								
B SIZE	-0.012	-0.047	0.005	0.271**	0.047	0.040	0.026	1.000							
B DUAL	0.010	0.005	-0.077**	-0.019	-0.068**	0.009	-0.001	-0.061*	1.000						
B MEET	-0.024	0.022	-0.012	0.062*	0.052*	-0.029	-0.027	0.007	0.022	1.000					
B INPEN	0.034	-0.430**	0.012	0.049*	-0.007	0.062*	0.047*	0.415**	0.139**	-0.081**	1.000				
M OWNE	-0.038	-0.030	-0.032	-0.06*	-0.045	-0.025	0.036	-0.11**	0.239**	0.016	0.083	1.000			
F OWNE	-0.034	0.007	0.035	0.001	-0.040	-0.017	-0.034	-0.014	-0.013	0.006	-0.048	-0.009	1.000		
INSTITUT	0.042	0.064*	-0.033	0.033	0.052*	0.021	-0.083**	0.055*	-0.139**	-0.049*	0.011	-0.170	-0.041	1.000	
B LOCKH	0.008	0.011	0.006	0.046	-0.082**	-0.053*	0.019	-0.010	0.035	-0.025	0.023	0.027	-0.028	-0.009	1.000

CAGE= CEO's age, measured by the difference between the CEO's date of birth and year of the study period. **CMALE**= CEO's male, take value 1 if CEO male, and 0 if female. **COVER**= CEO overconfidence, the proportion of CEO share ownership, options, and stock exercise. **F SIZE**= Firm size, the natural logarithm of firm's total assets. **F PROF**= profitability, measured by ROI (net income before tax divided by total assets). **F DIVID**= dividends ratio, measured by as cash dividends divided by net income for the same period. **F LEVER**= leverage ratio used as another proxy for CEO overconfidence, measured by total long-term debt divided by total assets. **FINDU**= industry type, measured by using the ISIN code, as stated by Jordanian Securities Depository Centre. **B SIZE**= board size, measured by the total numbers of the board. **BDUAL**= Board duality, a dummy variable that takes the value of one if the CEO and chairperson are the same person and zero if otherwise. **BMEET**= Board meeting, the number of meetings per year held by the board of directors. **BINDEP**= board independence, measured by the total number of outside directors. **MOWNE**= managerial ownership. Measured by the percentage of total shares held by executive directors divided by the total number of shares. **FOWNE**= family ownership, measured by the proportion of total shares owned by the family, a dummy variable would take one if a family or an individual hold 10% or more of equity, and the value zero if otherwise. **INSTITU**= institutional ownership, measured by dummy variable would take one if any institutional held shares and zero if otherwise. **BLOCKH**= block-holders ownership, measured by a dummy variable that takes the value of one if the firm has an external stockholder owning 5% or more of the outstanding shares, and the value of zero if otherwise.

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01, * Correlation is significant at the 0.05, . Correlation is significant at the 0.10

In terms of corporate characteristics and corporate governance factors such as management flexibility, corporate value and the number of family owners have a negative and significant relationship with debt ratio. The study found that profitable companies require less external financing since they can rely more on the income (Myers and Majluf, 1984). This result is consistent with previous studies (Al-Fayoumi et al., 2010; King & Santor, 2008).

Table 6
Regression Results

Variables	Coeff.	t-stat.	P. Value
Constant	.2067638	3.31	.001***
COVER	.0973374	7.39	.001***
CAGE	-.0015618	-2.72	.006***
CGEND	.1257617	3.88	.001***
FSIZE	3.85e-11	0.74	.461
FPROFIT	-.3025583	-5.81	.000***
FSECTOR	-.0036318	-0.17	.686
FDIVID	.032575	1.54	.123
BOARDSI	.0004294	0.10	.918
BOARDDD	-.0005617	-0.03	.980
BOARDM	-.0009713	-0.29	.775
BOARDI	.0105255	1.32	.187
MANAOW	-.00247	-0.03	.980
FAMILOW	-.000366	-1.77	.076*
BLOCKOW	-.0023372	-0.20	.840
INSTITOW	.0105255	1.32	.187

To address the endogeneity bias problem, the literature suggests two options; the use of instrumental variables (IV) (McKnight and Weir, 2009; Choi et al., 2010) and a simultaneous system equation (Hermalin & Weisbach, 1991; Cornett et al., 2008). This study used both Durbin and Hausman tests to check for bias in the endogenous and independent variables (Gujarati, 2003). The tests gave an X2 of 5.52% and 5.85% ($P < .0169$, $P < .0179$) respectively, which suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. Both instrumental variable and two-stage regression were therefore used to control for the endogeneity and simultaneity problems. The results of the two-stage regression are presented in Table 7. The coefficient of leverage ratio is positively and significantly ($p < .016$) related to the CEO's overconfidence. This result is in line with those of the panel regression random effect model reported in Table 6. The coefficient of CEO's age is significant and negatively associated with Leverage ratio ($p < .001$). The two-stage regression analysis shows similar results to the panel regression in Table 6, corroborating the results of Lin et al. (2014), who found a positive and simultaneous relation between CEO characteristics and internal control quality. The coefficient of leverage ratio is significant and positively ($P < .001$) related to gender, which suggests that these results are consistent with the main findings in Table 6. Regarding the control variables, the findings reported in Table 7 show similar results to those in Table 6, although, some values have greater significance in Table 7; nevertheless, the direction and significance of the association with leverage remain the same. In summary, the instrumental variable two-stage model results are consistent with the primary results presented in Table 6, implying that the simultaneity problem between leverage and CEO does not affect the results of leverage and other control variables.

Table 7
2-stage regression results

Variables	Coeff.	t-stat	P. Value
Constant	.2858471	11.13	0.000
COVER	-.0025205	-2.40	0.016***
CAGE	.1060139	4.70	0.001***
CGEND	.3024688	6.64	0.001***
FSIZE	2.37e-10	6.51	0.001***
FPROFIT	-.067299	-1.64	0.101*
FSECTOR	.0727807	4.30	0.000***
FDIVID	6.92e-12	0.82	0.413
BOARDSI	.0040664	1.99	0.047**
BOARDDD	.0140643	1.18	0.237
BOARDM	-.0011452	-0.55	0.584
BOARDI	.005462	1.33	0.183
MANAOW	-.0587541	-1.07	0.285
FAMILOW	-.0479093	-2.51	0.012***
BLOCKOW	-.0467553	-2.76	0.006***
INSTITOW	-.0008176	-0.09	0.929
R Sq. value			
P. value			

** Significant at the 0.01 level. ** Significant at the 0.5 level. * Significant at the 0.10 level.

Conclusions

The paper examines the impact of CEO on leverage among Nigerian listed companies over the period 2012 to 2021. We found that 95% of the sample is headed by men. The percentage of female directors is relatively low, 5%, still higher than the average of about 3% in several other countries. The overall results show that the CEO's trust in gender has a positive and significant relationship with leverage. The regression also shows a negative association between the degree of leverage and the age of CEOs, suggesting that older CEOs are less likely to receive compensation than younger CEOs. The findings of the study should be of interest to policy makers, administrators and experts on the impact of CEO characteristics on leverage, not only in Nigeria but also in other developing countries. In addition, the findings of this study may be of interest to investors, as this study introduces new evidence that shows the strength of companies in Nigeria.

The results will also appeal to shareholders, while law enforcement officials may find the results boost the CEO's performance and their potential influence within the executive team. Research will also be important to those who do it (such as researchers, investors, and those looking for different businesses). For these groups, it may be important to know what effect CEO has on leverage outcomes, and how this differs across different levels of decision-making power. Useful information and awareness of certain influences can help make governance more efficient and effective. This finding can be used to inform policy strategies to support the decision-making power of the CEO, because this study sheds light on the effect of the CEO on the extent of leverage. However, these results are based only on non-financial institutions, and future studies may focus on the financial sector, which plays an increasingly important role in economic development.

References

- Abdel-Fattah, T. M. H. (2008). Voluntary disclosure practices in emerging capital markets: The case of Egypt, University of Durham.
- Ahmad, Z., N. M. H. Abdullah, and S. Roslan. (2012). Leverage effect on firms performance: Focusing on consumers and industrial sectors on Malaysian firms. *International Review of Business Research Papers* 8 (5):137-155.
- Al-Akra, M., and P. Hutchinson. (2013). Family firm disclosure and accounting regulation reform in the Middle East: The case of Nigeria. *Research in Accounting Regulation* 25 (1):101-107.
- Al-Fayoumi, N., B. Abuzayed, and D. Alexander. (2010). Ownership structure and earnings management in emerging markets: The case of Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics* 38:28-47.
- Alicke, M. D. (1985). Global self-evaluation as determined by the desirability and controllability of trait adjectives. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 49 (6):1621.
- Alqatamin, R., Z. Ali, and T. Arun. (2017). The effect of CEOs' characteristics on forward-looking information. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*.
- Alzoubi, E. S. S., and E. S. S. Alzoubi. (2016). Disclosure quality and earnings management: Evidence from Nigeria. *Accounting Research Journal* 29 (4):429-456.
- Andriospoulos, D., K. Andriospoulos, and H. Hoque. (2013). Information disclosure, CEO overconfidence, and share buyback completion rates. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 37 (12):5486-5499.
- NGX, A. S. E. M. *Companies Control Department classification* 2015 [cited].
- Athanasakou, V., and K. Hussainey. (2014). The perceived credibility of forward-looking performance disclosures. *Accounting and Business Research* 44 (3):227-259.
- Athanasakou, V. E., N. C. Strong, and M. Walker. (2009). Earnings management or forecast guidance to meet analyst expectations? *Accounting and Business Research* 39 (1):3-35.
- Berger, P. G., E. Ofek, & Yermack, D. L. (1997). Managerial entrenchment and leveraged decisions. *The Journal of Finance*, 52(4):1411-1438.
- Bertrand, M., and A. Schoar. (2003). Managing with style: The effect of managers on firm policies. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 118 (4):1169-1208.
- Carpenter, M. A., M. A. Geletkanycz, and W. G. Sanders. (2004). Upper echelons research revisited: Antecedents, elements, and consequences of top management team composition. *Journal of Management* 30 (6):749-778.
- Chang, L. S., and K. S. Most. (1985). *The perceived usefulness of financial statements for investors' decisions*: University Presses of Florida Gainesville.
- Chen, Y., X. Zhang, and Z. Liu. (2014). Manager Characteristics and the Choice of Firm "Low Leverage": Evidence from China. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 4 (10):573.
- Cooper, A. C., C. Y. Woo, and W. C. Dunkelberg. (1988). Entrepreneurs' perceived chances for success. *Journal of Business Venturing* 3 (2):97-108.
- Cornett, M. M., A. J. Marcus, and H. Tehranian. (2008). Corporate governance and pay-for-performance: The impact of earnings management. *Journal of Financial Economics* 87 (2):357-373.
- Cornett, M. M., J. J. McNutt, and H. Tehranian. (2009). Corporate governance and earnings management at large US bank holding companies. *Journal of Corporate Finance* 15 (4):412-430.
- Cronqvist, H., A. K. Makhija, and S. E. Yonker. (2012). Behavioral consistency in corporate finance: CEO personal and corporate leverage. *Journal of Financial Economics* 103 (1):20-40.
- Custódio, C., and D. Metzger. (2014). Financial expert CEOs: CEO's work experience and firm's financial policies. *Journal of Financial Economics* 114 (1):125-154.
- Davidson III, W. N., B. Xie, W. Xu, and Y. Ning. (2007). The influence of executive age, career horizon and incentives on pre-turnover earnings management. *Journal of Management & Governance* 11 (1):45-60.
- Desai, M. A., D. Dharmapala, and W. Fung. (2005). Taxation and the evolution of aggregate corporate ownership concentration: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Faccio, M., M.-T. Marchica, and R. Mura. (2016). CEO gender, corporate risk-taking, and the efficiency of capital allocation. *Journal of Corporate Finance* 39:193-209.
- Fairchild, R. (2010). Behavioural corporate finance: existing research and future directions. *International Journal of Behavioural Accounting and Finance* 1 (4):277-293.
- Fairchild's, R. J. (2005). The effect of Managerial Overconfidence, asymmetric information, and moral hazard on leverage decisions. Available at SSRN 711845.
- Frank, M. Z., and V. K. Goyal. (2007). Corporate leverage: How much do managers really matter? 28. Frank, M. Z., and V. K. Goyal.

(2009). leverage decisions: which factors are reliably important? *Financial Management* 38 (1):1-37.

Graham, J. R., C. R. Harvey, and M. Puri. (2013). Managerial attitudes and corporate actions. *Journal of financial economics* 109 (1):103-121.

Gujarati, D. (2003). *Basic Econometrics Fourth Edition* McGraw Hill Gujarati, DN. (2003). *Basic Econometrics*: McGraw Hill. International Edition.

Hackbarth, D. (2008). Managerial traits and leverage decisions. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis* 43 (04):843-881.

Hambrick, D. C. (2007). Upper echelons theory: An update. *Academy of management review* 32(2):334-343.

Hambrick, D. C., and P. A. Mason. (1984). Upper echelons: The organization as a reflection of its top managers. *Academy of management review* 9 (2):193-206.

Harris, M., and A. Raviv. (1991). The theory of leverage. *the Journal of Finance* 46 (1):297-355.

Hermalin, B. E., and M. S. Weisbach. (1991). The effects of board composition and direct incentives on firm performance. *Financial management*: 101-112.

Huang, J., and D. J. Kisgen. (2013). Gender and corporate finance: Are male executives overconfident relative to female executives? *Journal of financial economics* 108 (3):822-839.

JSC, J. S. C. (2015). *General Information 2015* [cited 2-12 2015].

Katmun, N. (2012). *Disclosure quality determinants and consequences*, Durham University. 39.

King, M. R., and E. Santor. (2008). Family values: Ownership structure, performance and capital structure of Canadian firms. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 32 (11):2423-2432.

Kruger, J. (1999). Lake Wobegon be gone! The "below-average effect" and the egocentric nature of comparative ability judgments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 77 (2):221.

Landier, A., and D. Thesmar. (2009). Financial contracting with optimistic entrepreneurs. *Review of financial studies* 22 (1):117-150.

Langer, E. J. (1975). The illusion of control. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 32 (2):311-43.

Lemmon, M., L. X. Liu, M. Q. Mao, and G. Nini. (2014). Securitization and leverage in nonfinancial firms: An empirical investigation. *The journal of finance* 69 (4):1787-1825.

Li, T., Q. Munir, and M. R. A. Karim. (2017). Nonlinear relationship between CEO power and leverage: Evidence from China's listed SMEs. *International Review of Economics & Finance* 47:1-21.

Libby, R., and K. Rennekamp. (2012). Self-Serving Attribution Bias, Overconfidence, and the Issuance of Management Forecasts. *Journal of accounting research* 50 (1):197-231.

Lin, Y. C., Y. C. Wang, J. R. Chiou, and H. W. Huang. (2014). CEO Characteristics and Internal Control Quality. *Corporate Governance: An International Review* 22 (1):24-42.

Malmendier, U., and G. Tate. (2008). Who makes acquisitions? CEO overconfidence and the market's reaction. *Journal of financial economics* 89 (1):20-43.

Malmendier, U., G. Tate, and J. Yan. (2007). Corporate financial policies with overconfident managers: National Bureau of Economic Research.

Malmendier, U., G. Tate, and J. Yan. (2011). Overconfidence and early-life experiences: the effect of managerial traits on corporate financial policies. *The Journal of Finance* 66 (5):1687-1733.

Mason, E. S., and P. E. Mudrack. (1996). Gender and ethical orientation: A test of gender and occupational socialization theories. *Journal of Business Ethics* 15 (6):599-604.

Morellec, E. (2004). Can managerial discretion explain observed leverage ratios? *The Review of Financial Studies* 17 (1):257-294.

Myers, S. C., and N. S. Majluf. (1984). Corporate financing and investment decisions when firms have information that investors do not have. *Journal of Financial Economics* 13 (2):187-221.

Olokoyo, F. O. (2013). leverage and corporate performance of Nigerian quoted firms: A panel data approach. *African Development Review* 25 (3):358-369.

Peasnell, K. V., P. F. Pope, and S. Young. (2005). Board monitoring and earnings management: do outside directors influence abnormal accruals? *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting* 32 (7-8):1311-1346.

Richardson, G., G. Richardson, G. Taylor, G. Taylor, R. Lanis, and R. Lanis. (2016). Women on the board of directors and corporate tax aggressiveness in Australia: An empirical analysis. *Accounting Research Journal* 29 (3):313-331.

Ross, S. A. (1977). The determination of financial structure: the incentive-signalling approach. *The Bell Journal of Economics*: 23-40.

Salawu, R. O., and A. A. Agboola. (2008a). The determinants of leverage of large non-financial listed firms in Nigeria.

Salawu, R. O., and A. A. Agboola. (2008b). The determinants of leverage of large non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research* 2 (2):75-84.

Serfling, M. A. (2012). CEO age, underinvestment, and agency costs. *Eller College of Management, University of Arizona*.

Serfling, M. A. (2014). CEO age and the riskiness of corporate policies. *Journal of Corporate Finance* 25:251-273.

Singh, A., and A. Zammit. (2000). International capital flows: Identifying the gender dimension. *World Development* 28 (7):1249-1268.

Skala, D. (2008). Overconfidence in psychology and finance—an interdisciplinary literature review. *Bank i Kredyt* (4):33-50.

Skalpe, O. (2007). The CEO gender pay gap in the tourism industry—Evidence from Norway. *Tourism Management* 28 (3):845-853.

Svenson, O. (1981). Are we all less risky and more skillful than our fellow drivers? *Acta Psychologica* 47 (2):143-148.

Tomak, S. (2013). The impact of overconfidence on leverage in Turkey. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues* 3 (2):512-518.

Weinstein, N. D. (1980). Unrealistic optimism about future life events. *Journal of personality and social psychology* 39 (5):806.

Wen, Y., K. Rwegasira, and J. Bilderbeek. (2002). Corporate governance and leveraged decisions of the Chinese listed firms. *Corporate Governance: An International Review* 10 (2):75-83.

Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.

Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.

Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.

Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.

- Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.
- Lateef, O. M., Saheed, Z. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2015). Institutional factors and personal tax compliance in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(24), 146-157.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Onyabe, J. M., Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board gender diversity and earnings management: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation*, 18(3/4), 198-222.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tnushi, P. T., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Ownership structure and dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 10(1), 68-82.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improves intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Journal of Economic and Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim, A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of Nigeria listed insurance companies. *Int. Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Sustainability*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamidi, Y. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria: A case study approach. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8(2022), 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance and Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.

- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.
- Yahaya, O. A., Farouk, B. K. U., Lamidi, S. Y., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). Impact of competition on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(18), 52-61.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: An empirical investigation using Panel Data. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yim, S. (2013). The acquisitiveness of youth: CEO age and acquisition behavior. *Journal of financial economics* 108 (1):250-273.
- Yu, S., R. Lord, E. Peni, and S. Vähämaa. (2010). Female executives and earnings management. *Managerial Finance* 36 (7):629-645.
- Zeitun, R., G. Tian, and S. Keen. (2007). Macroeconomic determinants of corporate performance and failure: evidence from an emerging market the cNGX of Nigeria.
- Zeitun, R., & G. G. Tian. (2007). leverage and corporate performance: evidence from Nigeria. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 1(4), 3-17.